

Chemical control of ufra disease in transplanted rice

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We tested four nematicides, common salt, and zinc sulfate for control of ufra caused by the stem nematode

Ditylenchus angustus. Two-month-old BR4 plants with visible mottling and leaf chlorosis were collected from a farmer's field and planted 3 plants/pot in 3 replications for each treatment. Seven and 27 d after planting, 1.5 kg carbofuran 3%, 10.0 kg fenamiphos 5%, 10.0 kg disulfoton 10% 3.0 kg aldicarb 10% ai/ha, 67 kg common salt, and 20 kg zinc sulfate/ha were applied as basal, basal + foliar, or foliar. For foliar application, the chemicals were soaked 48 h in water, sieved through a fine cotton cloth, diluted to 120 ml to make an adequate amount to cover the leaf surface of the plants, and sprayed on the plants with a small hand sprayer. For

Effect of carbofuran 3% on ufra severity and yield of transplanted rice.^a Joydebpur, Bangladesh, 1984.

Carbofuran 3% (kg ai/ha)	Ufra severity (%)		Healthy panicles (%)	Yield (t/ha)
	Booting	Harvest		
0	81.2 a	69.7 a	30 c	05 b
0.5	73.7 a	49.4 a	51 b	1.0 b
1.0	49.6 ab	43.8 ab	56 ab	1.0 ab
1.5	28.3 b	31.3 b	69 a	1.6 a
F-values ^b	7.35*	4.78*	4.99*	8.10*
CV	23	21	17	31

^aAv of 4 replications. Column values with a common letter do not differ significantly at 0.05 level by DMRT. ^b* = significant at 0.05 level of significance.

basal + foliar treatment half the dose was used for each application. Control pots were sprayed with tap water.

At harvest, recovery was 64% with carbofuran, 69% with fenamiphos, and 73% with disulfoton. Plants treated with these nematicides yielded 14, 21, and 20 g/pot. There was no yield from other treatments. Secondary tillers of the three successful treatments were not ufra-infected. All tillers died in the other treatments.

We conducted a trial in an ufra-infested transplanted aman field to

identify the proper carbofuran dosage to be applied after plants show ufra symptoms. Carbofuran at 0.5, 1.0, or 1.5 kg ai/ha was incorporated in soil in 2-3 cm standing water at 1-mo intervals at tillering and late tillering. Carbofuran at 1.5 kg ai/ha gave best results (see table). In most cases, ufra infestation was less at harvest than at booting stage. The experiments showed that nematicides can control ufra in transplanted rice, even after symptoms have developed. ☞

Rice disease status in India

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Rice is planted on about 40.7 million ha in India. Yields often are substantially

reduced by disease. To monitor disease incidence, the Directorate of Plant Protection, Quarantine, and Storage and state departments of agriculture have organized insect pest and disease surveys since 1970. Twenty-six survey teams have covered standard routes through about 300,000 ha of rice land at 10-d intervals

since 1980. Disease severity has been rated using the 1980 Standard evaluation system for rice. The table shows major disease outbreaks and distribution.

Tungro virus is the most common disease. Most popular varieties are susceptible, including Tella Hamsa, Surekha, IET2508, IET1444, Co 40,

Present status and geographical distribution of major rice diseases in India.

State	Incidence of rice diseases ^a														
	B1	BS	NBLS	LSc	SR	ShB	ShR	Gld	FSm	KSm	Udb	BB	BLS	RTV	GSV
Andhra Pradesh	5-8 ^b	3-7 ^c	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	—	3-5 ^c	5-9 ^c	3-5 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	—	3-5 ^c	3-5 ^b	3-1 ^b	—
Assam	4-6 ^c	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	—	—	—	1-3 ^b	—	—	1-3 ^c	—	1-2 ^b	—
Bihar	3-5 ^b	3-7 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	3-5 ^c	3-5 ^b	3-5 ^b	1-3 ^c	1-3 ^c	—	0-1 ^b	3-5 ^c	1-3 ^b	3-7 ^b	—
Haryana	4-6 ^b	3-6 ^c	3-9 ^b	—	3-5 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-5 ^c	3-5 ^c	3-9 ^c	—	—	3-1 ^c	—	—	—
Karnataka	4-6 ^b	1-3 ^c	1-3 ^b	3-5 ^c	—	—	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-5 ^c	—	1-5 ^c	3-5 ^b	—	—	—
Kerala	—	1-3 ^b	—	1-3 ^b	—	3-5 ^c	—	—	—	—	1-5 ^b	1-3 ^b	—	1-2 ^b	—
Madhya Pradesh	5-7 ^b	3-6 ^c	0-1 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-7 ^c	1-3 ^c	5-9 ^c	5-7 ^d	1-3 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	3-5 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	—
Maharashtra	3-5 ^b	3-6 ^c	—	1-3 ^b	—	1-3 ^b	—	—	1-3 ^c	—	1-5 ^c	3-5 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	—
Orissa	4-6 ^b	3-6 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	1-3 ^b	—	0-1 ^b	3-5 ^c	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	—				
Punjab	1-3 ^b	2-5 ^b	3-5 ^b	—	3-7 ^c	3-5 ^b	3-7 ^d	3-5 ^c	1-5 ^b	—	—	5-7 ^b	3-5 ^b	1-3 ^b	—
Tamil Nadu	3-5 ^b	2-4 ^b	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	—	1-5 ^b	3-7 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-7 ^c	0-1 ^b
Uttar Pradesh	2-6 ^b	3-1 ^c	—	1-3 ^b	3-5 ^b	1-3	3-5 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-5 ^b	—	—	3-5 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-7 ^b	—
West Bengal	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	—	1-3 ^b	3-5 ^b	1-3	3-5 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	—	—	3-5 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-7 ^c	—

^a B1 = blast, BS = brown spot, NBLS = narrow brown leaf spot, LSc = leaf scald, SR = stem rot, ShB = sheath blight, ShR = sheath rot, Gld = glume discoloration, FSm = false smut, KSm = kernel smut, Udb = udbatta disease, BB = bacterial blight, BLS = bacterial leaf streak, RTV = rice tungro virus, GSV = grassy stunt virus. ^b Isolated/rare fields. ^c Scattered/sporadic. ^d Widespread.

NLR9672, Madhu, Vaigai, IET1722, TKM9, Kanchi, Rasi, Kannagi, ADT36, ADT31, TKM8, IR8, TNI, IR5, Co 25, Bhavani, Ponni, BCPI, and IR20. Other serious diseases include blast (Bl) and brown spot (BS).

Once minor diseases, bacterial blight (BB), sheath blight (ShB), sheath rot (ShR), and grain discoloration (Gld) are increasingly destructive and are beginning to affect almost all rice growing areas. False smut, bacterial leaf streak (BLS), stem rot, leaf scald,

udbatta, narrow brown leaf spot, and grassy stunt virus diseases also are increasing.

BB infection has been moderate to severe (3-7) in many states (see table) since 1980, and occurred in epidemic proportions in almost all of the Punjab in 1980 and 1981 kharif. Losses generally were 15-20% and sometimes rose to 40%. IR8, Jaya, and PR106, which are widely grown were highly susceptible.

BLS occurs widely but was worst in

Andhra Pradesh and the Punjab in 1980. Bl is common (see table) and attacks Jaya, Ratna, Basmati, Surekha, Mahsuri, Gurmatia, Phalguna, Kranti, IR8, and PR106. BS is a problem in upland and low fertility soils. ShR and Gl attack almost all high yielding varieties, including Phalguna, Surekha, Bangoli, PR106, IR8, Jaya, Co 40, Kranti, Ratna, and Mahsuri. However, Basmati, Mahsuri, Usha, Asha, and Pankaj varieties proved tolerant. *ℓ*

Recovery of virus from tungro (RTV)-infected leaves with or without leafhopper infestation

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Six-week-old TNI seedlings were caged with green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* that had fed on RTV-infected plants. RTV symptoms developed 2 wk after inoculation. Two or three new leaves were yellow or twisted, but the older leaves remained green and apparently healthy. Leaves with and without symptoms were taken from the infected plants and separately confined in test tubes for 1 d with new adult GLH. The GLH then were allowed individual 1-d inoculation access on 7d-old TNI seedlings. Inoculated seedlings were transplanted in pots and percent seedling infection was recorded in 2 wk.

GLH recovery of virus from leaves of TNI plants infected with RTV at 2 stages, IRRI, 1985.

Leaf position	Insects		
	Tested (no.)	With virus (no.)	With virus (%)
<i>6 wk after soaking</i>			
1st youngest	20	19	95
2d	17	12	71
3d	20	10	50
4th	—	—	—
<i>2-leaf stage</i>			
1st youngest	40	37	93
2d	40	35	88
3d	39	7	18
4th	40	5	13

All the GLH recovered virus from leaves with symptoms and 57% of GLH recovered virus from the older leaves without symptoms. GLH recovery of RTV was highest from younger leaves

(see table). Leaves also were collected from plants inoculated at second-leaf stage 1 mo after inoculation. Virus recovery was also highest from younger leaves (see table).

A method for producing *Rhizoctonia solani* inoculum for field inoculation

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Artificial inoculation is necessary for studying sheath blight (ShB) caused by *R. solani*. Growing the fungal colony on potato dextrose agar (PDA) plates and inoculation by placing agar blocks in leaf sheaths works well for laboratory and greenhouse studies, but is cumbersome in the field. We sought to develop more suitable methods of inoculum production for field studies.

Table 1. Growth of *R. solani* on different media, Bombuwela, Sri Lanka.

Medium	Colony diameter ^a (mm)			
	After 24 h	After 48 h	After 72 h	After 96 h
Chaff	11.3	35.5	84.0	84.3
Straw	10.0	26.0	33.0	68.3
WA	33.0	57.5	86.0	86.0 ^b
Husk	8.6	16.0	74.6	84.0
Sawdust	7.3	11.3	12.6	13.8
Grain	16.6	86.0	86.0 ^b	86.0 ^b
Chaff + grain	14.3	37.6	84.0 ^b	84.0 ^b
PDA	25.5	85.0	85.0 ^b	85.0 ^b
Agar + chaff	12.3	36.6	84.0	84.0
Rice dust	7.6	57.3	83.3	84.0

^a Av of 3 replications. ^b Started to produce sclerotia.

Table 2. Effect of different media on *R. solani* sclerotia production, Bombuwela, Sri Lanka.

Medium	Mycelial growth	Sclerotial initiation ^a	Sclerotial produced ^b (no.)
Chaff	Fast	10	94.3
Straw	Moderate	24	93
WA	Very fast	4	20.3
Husk	Moderate	6	17.6
Sawdust	Slow	3	7
Grain	Very fast	3	3000
Chaff + grain	Fast	3	490
PDA	Very fast	3	65.6
Agar + chaff	Fast	4	143.6
Rice dust	Fast	4	39.6

^a In days after inoculation. ^b Av of 3 replications.

We tested rice chaff, straw, dust, husk, and grain and sawdust for growing *R. solani*. Five grams of each medium and 15 ml of distilled water were placed in petri dishes and autoclaved at 15 psi at 121°C for 15 min. These plates and plates of PDA and water agar (WA) were inoculated with one fast-growing *R. solani* sclerotium, placed in the center of the dish. Colony growth was measured by surface diameter.

The same media were tested in 250-ml flasks by mixing 15 g of raw materials and 45 ml distilled water and autoclaving as before. One *R. solani* sclerotium was the inoculant and sclerotia were counted after 30 d. PDA and WA were used as checks. Each of the following media was